

Section: Philosophy

CRIME, CAPITALISM, AND REDEMPTION: RASKOLNIKOV IN THE CROW (2024) AND AN EXPLORATION OF CINEMATIC NIHILISM

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Abstract

The 2024 remake of *The Crow* revitalizes themes of nihilism and redemption found in classic literature, particularly Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment*. This paper examines the protagonist's resemblance to the "superfluous man" archetype in Russian literature, particularly Raskolnikov, while emphasizing the film's shift from a hyper-masculine hero to a more vulnerable figure. The narrative highlights love as a transformative force, drawing parallels with characters like Sonia Marmeladova and Shelly. By situating the modern *Crow* within contemporary cultural discourses surrounding masculinity, violence, and alienation, this analysis explores the character's evolution from a romantic terrorist to an emotionally complex figure, reflecting broader societal trends among today's disaffected youth.

Keywords: *The Crow*, nihilism, Dostoevsky, superfluous man, redemption, masculinity, Nietzsche, Raskolnikov, modern cinema, cultural analysis.

Introduction

In the realm of popular culture and contemporary cinema, violent classics are not simply being rehashed—they are being resurrected, drawing deeply from literature's most tortured and existential characters. The 2024 remake of *The Crow* is a prime example of how these films breathe new life into the complex ideas first articulated by Russian literary giants like Fyodor Dostoevsky, Ivan Turgenev, and Mikhail Lermontov. The main character, Eric Draven, bears striking similarities to characters such as Raskolnikov, Bazarov, and Pechorin—figures who represent the "superfluous man" of Russian literature, driven by a profound sense of alienation, nihilism, and moral conflict.

Unlike the 1994 adaptation starring Brandon Lee, where Draven was depicted as a hyper-masculine, avenging angel—part action hero, part psychopathic killer—the 2024 version transforms Draven into a much more vulnerable and childlike figure, evoking comparisons to Dostoevsky's Rodion Raskolnikov. This Draven is "a lost boy in a man's body," a fragile soul disconnected from the brutal, masculine world around him, and his journey of vengeance is less about domination and more about finding redemption through suffering and love. This is a marked departure from the traditional tropes of male avengers in cinema, illustrating a larger shift in how narratives of violence and morality are depicted today.

The Crow as a Reflection of Raskolnikov's Moral Dilemma

At the core of *The Crow*'s narrative is a violent retribution rooted in love, much like Raskolnikov's philosophical and moral struggles in *Crime and Punishment*. Both Eric Draven and Rodion Raskolnikov kill not out of pure malice, but out of a belief that their actions are justified within their own existential crises. Raskolnikov's infamous justification for murdering the pawnbroker is driven by his theory of the "extraordinary man"—those few individuals who possess the right to transcend conventional morality for the greater good (Dostoevsky, 1866). Similarly, Draven's violent rampage against those responsible for his girlfriend's death is less about vengeance in a traditional sense and more about his own crisis of identity, loss, and moral disintegration.

Philosophers like Friedrich Nietzsche have long commented on the allure of nihilism as a framework for understanding such figures. Bazarov from Turgenev's *Fathers and Sons* embodies a similar archetype: a radical nihilist who rejects society's conventions but whose emotional turmoil and eventual fall arise from an unfulfilled love, much like Eric Draven in his existential descent (Turgenev, 1862). Bazarov's rejection of both aristocratic and liberal ideals mirrors Draven's rejection of his former life and the systems that failed him, making them both products of their time and reflections of the human condition.

The Feminization of Tragedy: Shelly as Sonya Marmeladova

In the 2024 remake, Shelly—Draven's deceased lover—takes on a more complex and tragic role, reminiscent of Sonya Marmeladova in *Crime and Punishment*. Sonya, much like Shelly, is a symbol of suffering, redemption, and self-sacrifice. Sonya, despite her own fallen circumstances, becomes a moral compass for Raskolnikov, guiding him toward spiritual rebirth (Dostoevsky, 1866). The 2024 Shelly is no longer simply "the damsel in distress" of the original film, relegated to a backdrop of male violence; she now embodies a more multifaceted tragedy, perhaps even grappling with her own demons, such as addiction.

In *The Crow* (2024), the role of women is redefined in a way that aligns with the complex female characters of Russian literature. Shelly, much like Sonia in *Crime and Punishment*, is both sinner and saint—a woman whose suffering is central to the redemption of the male protagonist. In contrast to Shelly's fragility in the 1994 version, she now takes on aspects of both the "fatal woman" and the "pure savior," echoing the duality of Lermontov's heroines, Vera and Mary, in *A Hero of Our Time*. As Maxim Maximovich observed about Pechorin, "his soul was full of contradictions," a description that fits the 2024 *Crow* perfectly (Lermontov, 1840/2010).

In this portrayal, the female characters in *The Crow* parallel Russian literary archetypes like Tatyana from Pushkin's *Eugene Onegin* or Anna Sergeyevna from *Fathers and Sons*. These women, often subjected to the male protagonist's emotional conflicts, are central to the development of the male character's internal struggle. As Pushkin's Onegin ultimately realizes his love for Tatyana too late, Draven's love for Shelly and his inability to protect her from a violent death becomes the source of his posthumous torment (Pushkin, 1833/2005). Much like Pechorin from *A Hero of Our Time*, Draven is caught between his cynical worldview and his genuine emotions for the women in his life (Lermontov, 1840).

The Crow as Raskolnikov: Violence, Love, and Redemption

In the 2024 film, the Crow's violent quest to avenge Shelly recalls Raskolnikov's murder of the pawnbroker in *Crime and Punishment*. Both characters are terrorists in their own right—romantic, idealistic, and tortured souls who believe their acts of violence serve a higher moral purpose. Dostoevsky suggests that Raskolnikov killed the pawnbroker to "save" others, and similarly, the Crow's killing spree is presented as an act of moral vengeance against an exploitative capitalist figure who, much like the pawnbroker, metaphorically drains the life from those around her (Dostoevsky, 1866). The vampire-like quality of the film's antagonist reinforces a critique of modern capitalism, wherein, capitalist forces are depicted as vampiric and soul-consuming, preying on the vulnerable.

What makes the 2024 Crow distinct is its more explicit focus on love as a redeeming force. In the original 1994 film, Shelly is merely a damsel in distress, a woman who motivates the hero's violent revenge, but lacks her own agency. The 2024 version changes this dynamic entirely, bringing Shelly to the forefront as a tragic yet empowered character, much like Sonia Marmeladova in *Crime and Punishment* (Dostoevsky, 1866). In the film, she is portrayed as a drug addict and possibly a sex worker, echoing Sonia's profound suffering and spiritual strength. The Crow's love for Shelly drives him to his own destruction, mirroring how Raskolnikov's relationship with Sonia ultimately leads him to redemption through suffering. As Dostoevsky writes, "It was love that resurrected them," highlighting the theme of redemption through human connection (Dostoevsky, 1866/2014).

This reimagined Shelly is also reminiscent of Pushkin's Tatiana in *Eugene Onegin*, the woman who falls for a nihilistic hero but later transcends him through her emotional maturity (Pushkin, 1833/2005). Just as Onegin struggles with his feelings for Tatiana, the Crow is tortured by his love for Shelly, caught between his violent mission and the emotional weight of his attachment to her. These parallels make the 2024 Crow a distinctly literary figure—a nihilist who, like his predecessors, is ultimately doomed by the very forces that give him purpose.

Draven as a Modern-Day Superfluous Man

The figure of the "superfluous man" in Russian literature—men like Eugene Onegin, Pechorin, and Bazarov—represents a generation of characters disconnected from societal norms, trapped in their own intellectualism and nihilism. These figures reject social convention, flirt with self-destruction, and are ultimately isolated by their inability to reconcile their ideals with reality. Draven, in the 2024 Crow, takes on the mantle of the superfluous man in the contemporary cinematic landscape. Much like Pechorin, Draven appears to be caught in a cycle of existential contradiction. He is both strong and fragile, a figure who embodies a childlike vulnerability while being capable of immense violence. Lermontov's Pechorin is described as a man with "a strong body, yet a soul filled with contradictions," much like Draven, who despite his supernatural powers seems incapable of healing his own emotional wounds (Lermontov, 1840). The juxtaposition of Draven's physicality with his emotional fragility underscores his existential crisis—a theme central to both Pechorin and Raskolnikov.

Today's nihilists, as we have previously discussed (Panasiuk, 2024a), often retreat into online communities like Black Pill or incel spaces, where they struggle to find meaning in a world that feels increasingly disconnected from their emotional and existential needs (Panasiuk, 2024b). Like Raskolnikov, they seek validation through acts of rebellion, often violent, to prove their existence matters. The Crow's act of vengeance, therefore, is not just about Shelly's death; it is about asserting his place in a world that no longer recognizes him. This trend reflects a modern cultural phenomenon where the line between hero and antihero has become blurred, and violence is often romanticized as a form of existential expression.

The Incels and Modern Nihilism: Black Pill Philosophy in The Crow 2024

One of the most compelling aspects of *The Crow* (2024) is its portrayal of Draven as a figure deeply embedded in today's culture of nihilism. Raskolnikov's 19th-century philosophical nihilism finds its modern counterpart in today's Black Pill community (Panasiuk, 2024a). Draven, much like these modern nihilists, is driven by loss, futility, and a disconnection from society that leads him to violence. As we explored in our earlier studies, the incel phenomenon illustrates how the failure of romantic and emotional fulfillment can spiral into anger and destruction (Panasiuk, 2024b). Draven's character embodies this crisis: his violent acts are fueled less by revenge and more by the emotional void left by Shelly's death.

In this sense, Draven is a romanticized figure, embodying the deep alienation that has come to define modern nihilism in deeply Nietzschean terms, along with the search for the *Übermensch* within oneself (Nietzsche, 1885). In the 2024 reinterpretation of the film, his need to prove to himself that he was not a "trembling creature," but someone who "has the right," encapsulates the central question of Dostoevsky's novel. Fyodor Dostoevsky first pitched the idea of "the psychological account of a crime" to a publisher in 1865 (Dostoevsky, 1866). His journey reflects the idea that unfulfilled love can be a catalyst for violence, a theme that resonates within communities where emotional isolation and failure are tied to the pursuit of destructive ideologies. In recent work, we discussed how this dangerous cocktail of disenchantment and emotional turmoil often drives young men into extremism, seeking validation through violence and destruction (Panasiuk, 2024b). Draven's path is not unlike the path of those who, in today's world, seek out radicalized groups as a means of finding purpose in a life otherwise defined by emotional and psychological dislocation.

Nihilism and Terror in the 21st Century

Perhaps the most striking difference between the 1994 and 2024 versions of *The Crow* is how the nihilism of the protagonist resonates with the modern era. In 1994, Draven was an action hero operating within the familiar frameworks of Hollywood revenge tropes. In 2024, Draven's nihilism is more explicitly tied to the broader disillusionment and fragmentation of contemporary society. He is no longer the hyper-masculine, psychopathic antihero; instead, he is an idealized 21st-century terrorist—a romantic, disillusioned, addicted youth with shattered ideals. As literary critics have noted, this kind of nihilism has its roots in 19th-century Russian literature, where characters like Raskolnikov and Bazarov represented the rejection of traditional values and societal structures in the face of industrialization and capitalism

(Stellino, 2015; Kahn et al., 2018; Petrov, 2019; Stepenberg, 2019). Draven, in the 2024 film, stands as a modern reflection of these characters—alienated from a world that no longer makes sense to him, driven to violence as a way to assert control over his fractured reality.

The Crow's transformation into a modern-day Raskolnikov can be understood through the lens of nihilism, a philosophy that questions established moral values and societal structures. Bazarov, Turgenev's quintessential nihilist, dismisses the old order, much like today's Crow rejects traditional heroism. Nihilism, as described by Friedrich Nietzsche, is the "belief that life is without objective meaning, purpose, or intrinsic value" (Nietzsche, 1885/2005). This bleak outlook is embodied in the 2024 Crow, who, much like Raskolnikov, is driven to violence by a twisted sense of purpose. This characterization rings true in the new Crow, who lacks the assertive masculinity of his predecessor. Instead, he is a lost, disillusioned youth—more akin to an incel than a classic hero, as the incel phenomenon itself emerges from a place of nihilistic despair over unfulfilled desires and unmet expectations.

Nihilistic Morality and the "Sacred" Cause for Violence

According to Slovenian philosopher Slavoj Žižek (2024), the inability to mobilize great public causes for mass violence has led to a spontaneous moral sentiment among most people today, making them averse to killing. He argues that without a larger, "sacred" cause, individual concerns about killing become trivial, creating a moral vacuum where self-imposed limitations can easily be violated (Žižek, 2024). In this context, it is reminiscent of Rodion Raskolnikov from Dostoevsky's novel, who grapples with his own moral dilemmas and justifications for murder, illustrating the struggle between personal ethics and the idea of a greater cause. This resonates strongly in the new Crow, where the protagonist's love for Shelley drives his violent rebirth and ultimate quest for meaning.

Žižek (2024) also references Jacques Lacan's interpretation of Dostoevsky's ideas and the misattributed phrase "If there is no God, everything is permitted," often linked to Dostoevsky but originally popularized by Jean-Paul Sartre in his work *Being and Nothingness* (Sartre, 1943/2020). While this statement is widely cited, it doesn't appear directly in Dostoevsky's writings; instead, it reflects a conversation in *The Brothers Karamazov* about the implications of a nihilistic morality (Žižek, 2024).

Pop-Culture Cinematography Through the Lens of Dostoevsky

The 2024 remake of *The Crow* significantly departs from its 1994 predecessor, offering a more philosophically and culturally charged narrative. By transforming Eric Draven into a character who deeply resonates with Russian literary anti-heroes such as Rodion Raskolnikov and Evgeny Bazarov, the film taps into themes of nihilism, existential despair, and the tragic consequences of moral transgressions. This shift reflects how contemporary cinematography draws on classic literature to explore modern societal crises, with *The Crow* (2024) becoming a lens through which to examine today's cultural and emotional dissonances, akin to the existential and moral ambiguity of Dostoevsky's protagonists.

The Crow (2024) reinvents its titular character through a blend of Dostoevskian moral dilemmas and the "superfluous man" archetype, positioning the Crow as a

modern nihilist akin to Raskolnikov, Pechorin, and Bazarov. With a greater focus on love, emotional fragility, and existential alienation, the film presents a tragic hero who is both a romantic terrorist and a broken idealist. Much like in Dostoevsky's works, the message of the film is clear: redemption comes not through violence, but through love, suffering, and the willingness to confront one's own humanity.

The Superfluous Man and the Terrorist of the 21st Century

The figure of the superfluous man—seen in characters such as Raskolnikov, Bazarov, and Pechorin—finds its modern cinematic incarnation in Eric Draven. Like these literary anti-heroes, Draven is a man detached from society, driven by internal torment and moral ambiguity. The 2024 *Crow* moves away from the action-heavy narrative of the original, transforming Draven from a hyper-masculine avenger into a deeply vulnerable and emotionally conflicted character.

Where Brandon Lee's portrayal in *The Crow* (1994) fit the mold of a lone, violent hero, the new Draven is almost childlike in his emotional fragility. He is, as Lermontov's Pechorin was described, a man filled with contradictions (Lermontov, 1840/2010). As noted in our previous studies, today's superfluous men are often disenfranchised individuals, turning to violent ideologies out of a sense of lost identity and purpose. These figures reflect the modern terrorist archetype: disconnected from societal norms, fueled by unrequited love or emotional loss, and seeking validation through acts of violence (Panasiuk 2024a-b).

Draven's relationship with Shelly underscores this narrative. His violence is not born of a desire for justice but from a deeply personal loss, making him a 21st-century figure of romanticized, tragic violence. In this way, Draven aligns more closely with characters like Raskolnikov, who sought to transcend his misery through murder (Dostoevsky, 1866), or Pechorin, whose emotional turmoil led to his ultimate self-destruction (Lermontov, 1840). Both Draven and these literary figures illustrate how today's society continues to romanticize violent acts as a form of existential protest against emotional or social abandonment.

Conclusion

The 2024 remake of *The Crow* not only reimagines a classic revenge story but also infuses it with philosophical depth, drawing on themes from Russian literature. Eric Draven's character, a modern-day reflection of Raskolnikov and other Russian literary anti-heroes, is shaped by a complex interplay of nihilism, violence, and emotional loss. Through his journey, the film explores contemporary crises in masculinity and identity, placing *The Crow* within a broader cultural dialogue about the fragility of modern manhood and the dangerous allure of nihilistic violence.

By reimagining *The Crow* as a tragic figure with roots in Russian literary archetypes, the 2024 film not only revives a classic story but also imbues it with a deeper philosophical meaning. Like Raskolnikov, Draven seeks to transcend the boundaries of morality through violence, only to find himself trapped in his own psychological torment. Like Pechorin and Bazarov, Draven is a man out of place in the world, a superfluous figure whose love and nihilism collide in a fatalistic narrative arc. As we have discussed in previous research, these themes are not unique to Russian literature but resonate strongly in today's sociopolitical climate, where

feelings of alienation and disenchantment drive individuals toward violent extremes. Through Eric Draven's character, *The Crow* (2024) captures the essence of the "superfluous man" of the 21st century—a tragic, violent figure shaped by the loss of love and the failure to find meaning in a fragmented world.

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